

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF B.ED. STUDENTS IN RELATION TO SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE

Dr.Chandrakant Borse

Associate Professor in Education

College of Education,Nashik

Abstract

The present research study mainly aims at academic achievement of B.Ed.students in relation to social intelligence. A sample of 100 B. Ed. students of academic year 2011-2012 from four teacher-training colleges of Nashik was taken for the collection of data. The findings were exists a significant difference in the Social Intelligence of Male and Female B.Ed. students. Also exists a positive and significant relationship between the Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Male, Female and Total B.Ed. students.

Abstract: *Achievement, Social Intelligence*

Introduction

Teaching profession can directly influence on students through curriculum and indirectly through the social intelligence, emotional intelligence, attitudes, behaviors etc. Learning is a complex process, in it social intelligence indirectly influence the learning of the B.Ed. students. The important aspect related to learning is academic achievement of the B.Ed. students. The present research study mainly aims at Academic Achievement of the B.Ed.students with respect to social intelligence.

Statement of the Problem

Academic Achievement of B.Ed. students in relation to Social Intelligence

Operational Definitions of Specific Terms

Social Intelligence: Social Intelligence includes an awareness of situations and the social dynamics that govern them and a knowledge of interaction styles and strategies that help a person to achieve his/her objectives in dealing with others.

Academic Achievement: Academic Achievement is an excellence in all academic disciplines in a class as well as extracurricular activities.

Objectives of the Study:

- 1) To find out the relationship between Academic Achievement and Social Intelligence of Male B.Ed students
- 2) To find out the relationship between Academic Achievement and Social Intelligence of Female B.Ed students.
- 3) To find out the relationship between Academic Achievement and Social Intelligence of total B.Ed students.

Hypotheses:

- 1) There is no significant difference in the Social Intelligence of Male and Female B.Ed. students.
- 2) There is no significant relationship between the Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Male B.Ed.students.
- 3) There is no significant relationship between the Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Female B.Ed.students.
- 4) There is no significant relationship between the Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Total B.Ed.students.

Methodology of the Study:

Descriptive Survey Method was used for the present Study.

Variables:

Independent Variable: Social Intelligence

Dependent Variable: Academic Achievement

Sample:

A Sample of 100 B.Ed.students from the four Teacher training Colleges of Nashik City. It includes 50 Male and 50 female students.

Tools used for the Study:

Tool used for the present study is Social Intelligence Scale developed by N.K.Chandha and Usha Ganeshan.

Testing of Hypotheses:

Hypothesis-1: There is no significant difference in the Social Intelligence of Male and Female

B.Ed. students.

Sr.No	Variable	Group	Mean	S.D.	Df	t-Value	Level of Significance
1	Social Intelligence	Male B.Ed. Students	116.04	12.38	98	2.68	0.05
		Female B.Ed. Students	118.47	16.55			Significant

At 98 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance the t-value is 1.99. The calculated t-value is 2.68, which is more than the table value 1.99. Hence it is significant and Hypothesis-1 is rejected.

Therefore it was inferred that there was a significant relationship between the Social Intelligence of Male and Female B.Ed. student's t-ratio of Social Intelligence between Male and Female B.Ed. students was computed.

Hypothesis-2: There is no significant relationship between the Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Male B.Ed. students

Sr.No	Variable	No. of B.Ed. Students	Mean	Correlation Coefficient(r)
1	Social Intelligence	50	116.04	0.527
2	Academic Achievement	50	63.80	

The Correlation Coefficient calculated to be 0.527, is greater than the table value 0.312. Hence the Hypothesis-2 is rejected. So, there was a positive and significant relationship between the Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Male B.Ed. students.

Hypothesis-3: There is no significant relationship between the Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Female B.Ed. students.

Sr.No.	Variable	No. of B.Ed. students	Mean	Correlation Coefficient(r)
1	Social Intelligence	50	118.47	0.581
2	Academic Achievement	50	69.74	

The Correlation Coefficient between Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Female B.Ed.students is 0.581, which is more than the table value 0.312. Hence the Hypothesis-3 is rejected. Therefore it was inferred that there was a positive and significant relationship between Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Female B.Ed. students.

Hypothesis-4: There is no significant relationship between the Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Total B.Ed.students.

Sr.No.	Variable	No.of B.Ed students	Mean	Correlation Coefficient(r)
1	Social Intelligence	100	117.2	0.569
2	Academic Achievement	100	66.77	

The Correlation Coefficient between Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of total B.Ed. students is 0.569. This calculated value exceeds than the table value 0.196. Therefore the Hypothesis-4 is rejected. Hence it was inferred that there was a positive and significant relationship between Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of total B.Ed.students

Major Findings of the Study:

- 1) There is significant difference in the Social Intelligence of Male and Female B.Ed. students.
- 2) There is a positive and significant relationship between the Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Male B.Ed.students.
- 3) There is a positive and significant relationship between the Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Female B.Ed.students.
- 4) There is a positive and significant relationship between the Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement of total B.Ed.students.

Educational Implications:

This study concluded that B.Ed. students included both male and female have significant difference in the social intelligence. And also there is a positive and significant relationship between the social intelligence and academic achievement of B.Ed. students.

So if teacher educators want B.Ed. students to excel Academic Achievement, they should try to consider the social intelligence of the students.

B.Ed. students should develop Social Intelligence for carrying teaching-learning process effectively to become a successful teacher.

References:

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